

ACADEMIC PERSONNEL SUPERVISION AND INTEREST OF TEACHERS IN SCHOOL-RELATED EVENTS IN MALITA WEST DISTRICT, DAVAO OCCIDENTAL

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Abstract. The study aimed to investigate the correlation between academic personnel supervision and teachers' interest in school-related events. The researcher selected 165 elementary school teachers from Malita West District, Davao Occidental as the study participants. Stratified random sampling was employed to select the respondents. The research design used was non-experimental quantitative, utilizing a descriptive-correlational approach. Statistical analysis included the calculation of mean values and Pearson Moment Product Correlation. Findings revealed that academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental were rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. It was recommended that DepEd can also advocate for policies that ensure teachers have manageable workloads and sufficient time for involvement in extracurricular and school-related endeavors. Moreover, School administrators should cultivate a positive and inclusive school culture that appreciates teacher enthusiasm and involvement in school-related activities, acknowledging the advantages for both educators and students. It was further recommended the utilization of findings through publication in reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. academic personnel supervision
2. interest in school-related events
3. supervision

1. Introduction

The lack of interest among teachers in school-related events can have several detrimental impacts on educational processes. When teachers exhibit a lack of interest in school-related events, their involvement in extracurricular activities, committees, and professional development opportunities tends to diminish. This reduced engagement can lead to missed chances for collaboration, networking, and the exchange of best practices among colleagues. The im-

plications of teachers' limited engagement in school-related events are significant. It can lead to a lack of collaboration and knowledge-sharing among educators, hindering the collective effort to improve teaching practices and student outcomes. Moreover, it may contribute to a sense of isolation or disconnection among teachers, impacting morale and job satisfaction. Addressing this issue requires fostering a culture of active participation, continuous learn-

ing, and collaboration within the school community. In Finland, it was found that a lack of interest among teachers may contribute to a negative or uninspiring school environment, affecting student morale, motivation, and engagement. When teachers lack interest in their work or in participating in school-related events, it can create a domino effect that impacts the entire school environment. Students are highly perceptive and can sense when their teachers are not fully engaged or passionate about their work. As a result, a negative or uninspiring atmosphere may pervade the school, affecting student morale, motivation, and overall engagement in learning activities (Havia, Lutovac, Komulainen Kaasila, 2022). Similarly, Taghizadeh and Hasani Yourdshahi (2020) reported that a study conducted in Iran showed that if teachers are not actively involved in these events, it can hinder efforts to build strong partnerships between the school and the community, potentially impacting support for educational initiatives and programs. When teachers are not actively involved in school-related events, it represents a missed opportunity to strengthen the bonds between the school and the community. These events often serve as platforms for collaboration, communication, and relationship-building among various stakeholders, including teachers, parents, students, and community members. Taking things in Philippine setting, Barcelona, Daling, Doria, Balangiao, Mailes, Chiang and Ubatay (2023) reported that if teachers are not actively involved in school-related activities, students may have limited access to these sources of support. This lack of engagement can impact students' overall well-being and academic success. It was emphasized that when teachers are not actively involved in school activities, students may have limited access to these resources, hindering their ability to address academic challenges, seek assistance with personal issues, or access extracurricular opportunities. Thus, students may feel less comfortable reaching out to teachers for help with personal challenges such as mental health issues, family problems, or peer conflicts, which can impact their overall well-being and resilience. Several studies showed the link of academic personnel supervision on interest of teachers in school related events. For instance, Rusdiana, Huda, Mu'in, and Kodir (2020) discovered that favorable personnel supervision can elevate teachers' engagement in school-related activities by nurturing a supportive and motivating atmosphere. When educational administrators furnish constructive feedback, acknowledge teachers' endeavors, and provide avenues for professional advancement, it fosters a climate where educators feel valued and recognized for their contributions. This acknowledgment and support can inspire teachers to actively participate in various school events, fostering a culture of collaboration and commitment within the educational institution. Similarly, Renata, Wardiah, and Kristiawan (2019) proposed that positive personnel supervision can create a supportive environment where teachers feel empowered to take on leadership roles and contribute their ideas to the planning and organization of school-related activities. The research gap lies in conducting a correlational study on academic personnel supervision by school heads and teachers' interest in school-related events. While existing research has explored the impact of supervision on various aspects of teaching and school dynamics, there is limited empirical evidence specifically examining its relationship with teachers' engagement in school events. Understanding this correlation is crucial as it sheds light on how leadership practices influence teachers' involvement in extracurricular activities, professional development opportunities, and community engagement initiatives. Thus, it is on this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Davao Occidental using a quantitative

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

approach. Specifically, the researcher used a descriptive correlational design through regression analysis to understand the interest of teachers in school-related events as determined by academic personnel supervision, which is found to be scarce. Addressing this research gap can provide insights into effective strategies for promoting teacher engagement and enhancing overall school culture and effectiveness. This study explored the influence of academic personnel supervision of school heads on the interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. A descriptive correlational research design with regression analysis was used. The data was collected from the elementary school teachers using survey questionnaires which was pilot tested and validated. Moreover, the study was expected to benefit several individuals and groups in academe. For instance, research in this area may provide DepEd with valuable insights into the factors that influence teacher interest and engagement in school-related events. This knowledge may inform the development of policies and guidelines aimed at enhancing teacher participation in extracurricular activities. More so, policies based on research findings can contribute to improved education quality by fostering a more vibrant and engaging school environment. Increased teacher interest can positively impact

students' academic performance and overall school experience. School heads can benefit from understanding how supervision practices influence teacher enthusiasm. This knowledge enables them to adapt their leadership styles and practices to create a supportive and motivating school climate. Adding more, research findings can help principals foster a positive school culture that values and recognizes teachers' contributions to school-related events. This, in turn, can lead to higher levels of staff morale and job satisfaction. Further, teachers may use research insights to advocate for professional development opportunities related to extracurricular activities. They may seek roles that align with their interests and strengths, fostering personal and career growth. Moreover, understanding the factors that boost enthusiasm can lead to increased job satisfaction. Teachers who are actively engaged in school-related events often report higher levels of job satisfaction and a greater sense of fulfillment. Furthermore, studies in this area contribute to the body of educational research, providing a deeper understanding of the dynamics between supervision, teacher interest, and student outcomes. In addition, research findings may identify gaps in knowledge and open doors for further investigation, stimulating more research on teacher motivation, leadership, and school culture.

As shown in Figure 1, the study is consisting of two variables. The independent variable of the study is academic personnel supervision or the process of overseeing and managing educators, teachers, and other instructional staff in an educational institution. The measures of academic personnel supervision according to Demo et al. (2012) are inclusive decision making or the process of involving various stakeholders, including teachers, staff, parents, students, and community members, in the decision-making processes related to school policies, programs, and initiatives; fair evaluation or the systematic and equitable assessment of a school leader's performance and leadership qualities; alignment with ethical standards or the adherence to a set of ethical principles and values in their leadership roles within educational institutions; and community engagement or the active involvement of various community stakeholders in the decision-making processes, programs, and initiatives of the school. The dependent variable of the study is interest in school-related events or the degree of enthusiasm, engagement, and active participation demonstrated by educators in various school-related events, initiatives, and tasks beyond their core teaching responsibilities. According to Abdulla Al Kaabi (2015) the measures of interest in school-related events are passion for education or the strong and genuine enthusiasm, dedication, and commitment that teachers have toward the process of teaching and learning; commitment to student success or the teacher's unwavering dedication to the academic, personal, and overall well-being of their students; resourcefulness or the teachers' ability to creatively and effectively find and utilize a wide range of educational resources, strategies, and solutions to address challenges and enhance the learning experience for their students; and role modelling or the practice of educators demonstrating positive behaviors, values, attitudes, and ethical standards to their students through their own actions and choices.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, ethical consideration, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. It also worth noting that in the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized quantitative research, specifically the descriptive-correlational technique, to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. As characterized by Fischer et al. (2014), methodologies and strategies were employed to gather and scrutinize numerical data systematically and impartially, aiming to comprehend phenomena, correlations, or trends. These methods entailed employing statistical analysis to extract insights and make deductions from the data. Quantitative research involved the collection and analysis of numerical data to examine various aspects of phenomena, relationships, or patterns within a structured framework. This type of research relied heavily on quantifiable measures and statistical techniques to draw objective conclusions based on empirical evidence. Researchers often employed surveys, experiments, or observational studies to

gather data, which was then subjected to statistical analysis to identify trends, correlations, or significant differences. According to Skinner (2020), quantitative research methods emphasized objectivity and standardization, aiming to reduce bias and subjectivity during data collection and analysis. This approach enhanced the credibility and accuracy of research findings, enabling researchers to extrapolate results from a sample to a broader population. By employing techniques such as random sampling and statistical analysis, researchers could draw conclusions about larger populations, thereby enhancing the external validity of the study. On one hand, Rahi (2017) defined descriptive research techniques as strategies that involve methods utilized to depict, observe, and analyze the characteristics, behaviors, or phenomena of interest without exerting influence or manipulation. The primary objective was to offer a comprehensive portrayal of the subject being studied, prioritizing the depiction of existing conditions rather than delving into causality. Descriptive research typically employed a range of observational approaches, surveys, case studies, and archival investigations. Loeb et al. (2017) emphasized that descriptive research was instrumental in establishing foundational information concerning a specific phenomenon or population. By delineating the current state of affairs, researchers could pinpoint trends, patterns, and norms, serving as benchmarks for future comparisons. Additionally, descriptive research enabled researchers to delineate and characterize various attributes, traits, or features of a population, group, or phenomenon, including demographic particulars, behaviors, attitudes, and other pertinent factors. On the other hand, Stangor and Walinga (2019) characterized correlational research design as a form of non-experimental research employed to investigate the connection between two or more variables. This method entailed gauging the degree to which alterations in one variable corresponded with alterations in another, without

manipulating either variable. The aim was to ascertain whether there existed a statistical correlation between the variables and to discern the direction and magnitude of this association. According to Frazier (2013), correlational research served as a vital tool in advancing knowledge across diverse domains by unveiling relationships between variables, generating hypotheses, and informing practical applications and interventions. Despite the limitations inherent in correlational studies, such as the inability to establish causality, they furnished valuable insights that complemented experimental research endeavors and enriched our comprehension of intricate phenomena. In this study, the researcher intended to examine academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events. A descriptive-correlational research approach was deemed appropriate for investigating the relationships among these variables without manipulating them. In this context, academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events were naturally occurring variables that could be assessed and analyzed to determine their correlations. Moreover, when employed thoughtfully and mindful of its constraints, a descriptive-correlational research design had the potential to yield valuable insights into the intricate dynamics between academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events within educational contexts.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the elementary school teachers in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. In this study, the 165 respondents were selected through stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling according to Leedy and Ormrod (2018) is a sampling technique in which the population is divided into distinct subgroups or strata based on certain characteristics that are relevant to the research. Within each stratum, a random sample is then selected independently. This method ensures

that each subgroup within the population is adequately represented in the final sample, which can improve the accuracy and precision of the study's results. In implementing the stratified random sampling technique with the location of schools in Malita West District, Davao Occidental as the strata, several key considerations were taken into account to ensure the accuracy and representativeness of the sample. Firstly, the district was divided into distinct geographic areas or locations, which served as the basis for the strata. This division was informed by the administrative boundaries of the district, such as barangays or zones, to ensure clear demarcation and avoid overlap between strata. Once the locations were identified, the next step was to determine the number of schools within each location. This information was crucial for allocating appropriate sampling weights to each stratum, ensuring proportional representation in the final sample. Additionally, data on student enrollment, demographic characteristics, and academic performance have been considered to further inform the stratification process. Random selection within each stratum was conducted to choose the sample schools. This involved using randomization techniques to select schools from a comprehensive list of all schools within each location. By employing random selection, every school within the district had an equal chance of being included in the sample, minimizing selection bias and increasing the validity of the findings. Moreover, the primary

The second part of the instrument was about the teachers' interest in school-related events, which was intellectualized by Abdulla Al Kaabi (2015) and divided into four domains, namely: a passion for education, commitment to student success, resourcefulness, and role modeling. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items in each dimension under each domain. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research

consideration of this study was to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The inclusion criteria are as follows: currently employed teachers who are actively teaching in schools within the target district or area; at least one year or more, to ensure that the respondents have sufficient experience to provide meaningful insights into their perceptions and experiences with academic personnel supervision and school events; and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed the questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument concerned about the academic personnel supervision which was conceptualized by Demo et al. (2012). The questionnaire was consists of four domains namely: inclusive decision making; fair evaluation; alignment with ethical standards; and community engagement. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items each dimension under each domain. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale.

questionnaire. In order to facilitate the gathering of the needed data, the researcher sought the approval of the Dean of the Graduate School

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The academic personnel supervision is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The academic personnel supervision is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The academic personnel supervision is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The academic personnel supervision is seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The academic personnel supervision is never observed.

Note. The descriptive levels indicate the frequency of academic personnel supervision observations.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The interest of teachers in school-related events is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The interest of teachers in school-related events is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The interest of teachers in school-related events is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The interest of teachers in school-related events is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The interest of teachers in school-related events is never manifested.

Note. The descriptive levels indicate the frequency of interest manifestation in school-related events by teachers.

in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao naires. Subsequently, the endorsement from City, to conduct this study. Additionally, the researcher requested ethical clearance from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee (REC) before gathering data using the validated question- that was sent to the Schools Division Super-

intendent to request permission to conduct the study in the selected public schools. After securing the endorsement from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS), the researcher sought approval to conduct the study in the selected three public schools by writing to the principals. The endorsement letter from the SDS was presented to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Malita West District in Davao Occidental to conduct the study. The researcher identified and recruited one hundred sixty-five elementary school teachers from Malita West District in Davao Occidental. Inclusion criteria have included factors such as currently employed teachers who are actively teaching in schools within the target district or area; at least one year or more, to ensure that the respondents have sufficient experience to provide meaningful insights into their perceptions and experiences with academic personnel supervision and school events; and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Prior to data collection, the researchers obtained informed consent from all participants, explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Respondents were given the opportunity to ask questions and clarify any concerns before agreeing to take part in the study. The researcher explained that the survey questionnaires measure their perception of school heads' academic personnel supervision and teachers' interest in school-related events. After which, these questionnaires were distributed to elementary school teachers in Malita West District in Davao Occidental. The data collected through these questionnaires served as the basis for analyzing the influence of school heads' academic personnel supervision on the teachers' interest in school-related events. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, each respondent's scores were tallied and the data was organized per indicator. After which, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. In the context of the study on the influence of school heads' academic personnel supervision on the interest of teachers in school-related events, data, data collection involved implementing survey questionnaires. These questionnaires were distributed to elementary school teachers in Malita West District in Davao Occidental. The survey questionnaires were designed to gather information on various aspects related to school heads' academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events, data. Respondents were asked to provide their perceptions, attitudes, and experiences through the survey questions. The data collected through these questionnaires served as the basis for analyzing the which domains of school heads' academic personnel supervision significantly influence the interest of teachers in school-related events. The collected survey questionnaires from elementary school teachers in Malita West District in Davao Occidental, were carefully organized and compiled. Each questionnaire response was entered into a database or spreadsheet software for systematic management. Once the data was collated, statistical analyses were conducted to examine the relationships between variables. This included techniques such as correlation analysis to explore the associations between school heads' academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events, data. Further, regression analysis was employed to investigate the influence of school heads' academic personnel supervision on the interest of teachers in school-related events. Regression analysis was utilized to explore the influence of school heads' academic personnel supervision practices on teachers' interest in school-related events with inclusive decision making, fair evaluation, alignment with ethical standards, and community engagement components. The researcher examined the relationship between supervision practices and teachers' levels of

interest in events that involved these domains. This analysis helped identify the extent to which supervision practices contributed to enhancing teachers’ interest in school-related events.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between academic personnel supervision and interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of academic personnel supervision and teachers’ interest for school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental; and the significant relationship between academic personnel supervision and teachers’ interest for school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental.

Table 1. Summary of Academic Personnel Supervision in Malita West District, Davao Occidental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Inclusive Decision Making	3.42	Extensive
Fair Evaluation	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Alignment with Ethical Standards	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Community Engagement	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.36	Moderately Extensive

Table 1 shows the summary on academic personnel supervision in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. It shows that the overall mean of teaching personnel supervision is 3.36 which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. This suggests that the supervision and administration of teachers and other academic personnel in educational settings are occasionally noted. This observation underscores the importance of effective oversight and management practices to ensure the smooth functioning of educational institutions. This aligns with Ahmad and Saefurrohman’s (2020) perspective that supervising academic personnel ensures adherence to established teaching quality standards. Through guidance, feedback, and support, school administrators can maintain teaching consistency and effectiveness, thereby improving the overall quality of education within the institution. Effective supervision also fosters professional growth among teachers, enabling them to continually

enhance their teaching skills and methodologies. Moreover, academic personnel supervision in terms of inclusive decision making acquired the highest mean score of 3.42 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while, academic personnel supervision in terms of fair evaluation got the lowest mean score of 3.32 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. The outcome supports Kristiawan, Nizarani,

and Syamsidar’s (2019) idea that supervision plays a vital role in maintaining and improving teaching quality. It ensures that educators follow best practices, align their teaching methods with curriculum standards, and utilize effective instructional approaches. Essentially, supervision serves as a mechanism to monitor and support teachers in their professional endeavors, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of teaching quality and the overall effectiveness of educational practices.

Table 2. Summary on Interest of Teachers in School-Related Events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Passion for Education	2.96	Moderately Extensive
Commitment to Student Success	3.04	Moderately Extensive
Resourcefulness	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Role Modelling	3.47	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.20	Moderately Extensive

Shown in the Table 2 is the summary of interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. As shown in the table, interest of teachers in school-related events obtained an overall mean score of 3.20 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the elementary school teachers. This suggests that teachers occasionally show a readiness to participate in various aspects of the school community, such as extracurricular activities, committees, and professional development initiatives. This aligns with Martins et al.’s (2022) argument that teachers’ engagement in school-related events holds significance for enhancing teaching practices at advanced levels. It can contribute to cultivating a fa-

vorable school atmosphere, facilitating professional growth, and enhancing student achievements. Through active involvement in school events, teachers can collaborate with peers, exchange insights, and stay abreast of evolving educational methodologies and standards. Adding more, results in Table 2 show that teachers’ interest in school-related events in terms of role modeling acquired the highest mean score of 3.47 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, teachers’ interest in school-related events in terms of passion for education acquire the lowest mean score of 2.96 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the teachers in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. This corresponds with the perspective of

Muñoz-Hurtado (2019) that teachers' enthusiasm for school events nurtures a community spirit and promotes collaboration among various stakeholders, including educators, students, parents, and administrators. When teachers actively participate in school events with genuine interest, they play a pivotal role in fostering a supportive school environment marked by mutual respect, trust, and common objectives. Their involvement contributes to strengthening the bonds within the school community and reinforces the sense of belonging among all members. Through their active engagement, teachers demonstrate their commitment to the collective well-being and success of the school. The results of the analysis of the relationship between academic personnel supervision and the interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 11 shows that academic personnel supervision has a significant positive relationship with teachers' interest for school-related events with a p-value of .000 that

This supports the view of Rusdiana et al. (2020) that positive supervision from school leaders can boost teachers' interest in school events by creating a supportive atmosphere. Offering constructive feedback, recognizing teachers' efforts, and enabling their professional growth instill a sense of worth and acknowledgment among educators. Adding more, the result is congruent to Renata's et al. (2019) proposition that positive personnel supervision can create a supportive environment where teachers feel empowered to take on leadership roles and contribute their ideas to the planning and organization of school-related activities. In such an environment, teachers are encouraged to contribute their insights, ideas, and expertise,

is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .466, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of academic personnel supervision improved, teachers' interest in school-related events also significantly improved. More so, the results in the table show that inclusive decision-making, fair evaluation, alignment with ethical standards, and community engagement significantly correlated with teachers' interest in school-related events, as evidenced by correlation coefficient values of 0.372, 0.210, 0.232, and 0.291, respectively. Thus, this led to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between academic personnel supervision and teachers' interest for school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. The results indicate that positive personnel supervision plays a crucial role in bolstering teachers' enthusiasm for school-related events. When school leaders adopt a supportive and encouraging approach, providing constructive feedback, acknowledging teachers' contributions, and facilitating avenues for their professional advancement, it nurtures a climate of appreciation and value among educators.

thereby enhancing the overall quality and effectiveness of school activities. This collaborative approach not only enriches the experiences of both teachers and students but also strengthens the sense of ownership and engagement within the school community. Lastly, the result corroborates with Transformational Leadership Theory by Burns (1978) which pointing out that transformational leaders inspire and motivate their followers by articulating a compelling vision of the future and encouraging them to strive towards common goals. In the context of personnel supervision, positive and supportive feedback from supervisors can inspire teachers to see the value and importance of participating in school events. By highlighting the impact

Table 3. Relationship Between Academic Personnel Supervision and Interest of Teachers in School-Related Events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental

Academic Personnel Supervision	Interest in School-Related Events	r-value	p-value
Decision			
Inclusive Decision Making	0.372*	0.000	Reject H0
Fair Evaluation	0.210*	0.003	Reject H0
Alignment with Ethical Standards	0.232*	0.001	Reject H0
Community Engagement	0.291*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Academic Personnel Supervision	0.466*	0.000	Reject H0

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$

Legend. Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 > r > 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$ of these events on student learning and school culture, supervisors can motivate teachers to actively engage and contribute

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusion and recommendation. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the relationship between academic personnel supervision and the interest of teachers in school-related events utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 165 elementary school teachers in Malita West District, Davao Occidental, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The extent of academic personnel supervision in Malita West District, Davao Occidental, in terms of Inclusive Decision Making 3.42 or extensive, Fair Evaluation 3.32 or moderately extensive, Alignment with Ethical Standards 3.35 or moderately extensive, Community Engagement 3.36 or moderately extensive. The overall mean is 3.36, with the descriptive equivalent of moderately extensive. Academic personnel supervision in Malita West District in Davao Occidental was rated as moderately extensive descriptively. Also, academic personnel supervision in terms of fair evaluation, alignment with ethical standards, and community engagement

were rated as moderately extensive, while academic personnel supervision in terms of inclusive decision-making was found to be extensive. The extent of Interest of Teachers in School-Related Events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental, in terms of Passion for Education, 2.96 or moderately extensive; Commitment to Student Success, 3.04 or moderately extensive; Resourcefulness, 3.31 or moderately extensive; Role Modelling, 3.47 or extensive. The overall mean was 3.20 or moderately extensive. The interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District in Davao Occidental received a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, interest in school-related events in terms of passion for education, commitment to student success, and resourcefulness was rated as moderately extensive, while interest in school-related events in terms of role modelling was found to be extensive. Academic personnel supervision has a significant positive relationship with teachers' interest in school-related events in Malita West District. Meanwhile, academic personnel supervision in terms of inclusive decision-making, fair evaluation, alignment with ethical standards, and community engagement was found to be significantly correlated with teachers' interest in school-related events.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The moderate descriptive rating on academic personnel supervision in Malita West District in Davao Occidental indicated that occasional oversight and management of teachers and academic staff in educational environments are observed. The moderate descriptive rating on the interest of teachers in school-related events in Malita West District in Davao Occidental denoted that teachers occasionally demonstrate a willingness to engage in diverse aspects of the school community, including extracurricular activities, committees, and professional development initiatives. Academic personnel supervision has a significant positive relation-

ship with the teachers' interest in school-related events in Malita West District, Davao Occidental. The findings suggest adequate personnel supervision is vital in enhancing teachers' interest in school-related activities. When school leaders adopt a supportive stance, offering constructive feedback, recognizing teachers' efforts, and promoting their professional development, it fosters an environment of appreciation and recognition among educators.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education (DepEd) should institute acknowledgment and incentive initiatives to commend and incentivize teachers who actively engage in school-related events and contribute to fostering a positive school environment. Implementing acknowledgment and incentive programs within the Department of Education (DepEd) could significantly contribute to recognizing and motivating teachers who actively participate in school-related activities. By acknowledging their efforts and contributions, DepEd can reinforce a culture of appreciation and recognition within the education sector. These initiatives could include various forms of recognition, such as awards, certificates of appreciation, or public commendations during school assemblies or staff meetings. School administrators should cultivate a positive and inclusive school culture that appreciates teacher enthusiasm and involvement in school-related activities, acknowledging the advantages for both educators and students. When school administrators acknowledge and appreciate teacher enthusiasm for school-related activities, it fosters a sense of belonging and morale among educators. Feeling valued and recognized for their efforts motivates teachers to actively engage in various school events and initiatives. This, in turn, contributes to a more positive and collaborative work environment where teachers feel empowered to share ideas, collaborate with colleagues, and contribute to the overall improvement of the school community. Teachers should partici-

pate actively in school-related events, extracurricular activities, and initiatives, acknowledging the beneficial effects of such involvement on the school community and students. Active participation in school events and initiatives provides teachers with valuable opportunities for professional growth and collaboration. Engaging in workshops, professional development seminars, or collaborative planning sessions allows teachers to expand their knowledge, share best practices, and stay current with educational trends and research. This continuous learning and collaboration enhance teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Future researchers must conduct research on the relationship between teacher enthusiasm, school-related events, and student outcomes to provide evidence-based insights into the benefits of teacher involvement. Researchers must identify and disseminate best practices in teacher supervision and support that enhance teacher enthusiasm and participation in school events. There is a need for research that focuses on identifying and disseminating best practices in teacher supervision and support. By examining effective strategies for fostering teacher enthusiasm and participation in school events, researchers can provide evidence-based recommendations to school administrators and policymakers. This research can inform the development of comprehensive professional development programs, mentoring initiatives, and leadership practices that empower teachers to play an active role in the school community.

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